

A Comparative Study on Production of Graphene Quantum Dots from Coffee Beans and Tea Leaves Extract

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Abstract

In recent years, the importance of nanoparticle synthesis and application has increased, and as a result, more research has been conducted on nanoscience and nanotechnology. In particular, research on the production of environmentally friendly, less wasteful, low-cost, and multifunctional nanomaterials has increased dramatically. Some studies have been conducted on natural organic waste materials such as coconut husk, nutmeg seed, mint leaves, coffee beans, and tea leaves for producing nanostructures. Using organic waste materials as a source of nanostructures helps us save on disposal costs and helps the environment. Many different types of nanomaterials can be synthesized from organic waste materials such as, metallic nanoparticles, quantum dots, carbon-based nanomaterials, etc. Graphene quantum dots (G-QDs) are nanosized, two-dimensional particles, with sizes less than 100 nm that have amazing properties like being biocompatible, non-toxic, highly soluble, adjustable light emission, and photo-induced electron transfers. There are two main methods: top-down and bottom-up, which are used for the production of quantum dots. The microwave-assisted method is frequently used. Herein, we have envisaged synthesizing and characterizing G-QDs from organic waste materials, such as waste coffee grounds and tea leaves. Briefly, coffee beans and tea leaves were dried, ground, weighted, and extracted. A certain amount of coffee extract and tea leaf extract were used as precursors for the synthesis of G-QDs under the different conditions. The purification of G-QDs in this experiment was carried out by a high-speed (9000 rpm) centrifuge method. The synthesized G-QDs were characterized by UV-visible spectroscopy (UV-Vis), Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (FT-IR), Dynamic Light Scattering (DLS) and Zeta potential. The characterization results indicate that the highly photoluminescent G-QDs were successfully manufactured. So, the structures of the final products were verified using spectroscopic methods such as UV-VIS, FT-IR, and DLS. This research focuses on creating high-quality G-QDs from biomass for practical use in sensing, photocatalysis, and biomedical applications.

Keywords: Waste coffee grounds, waste tea leaves, Graphene quantum dots, Microwave-assisted method

Introduction

Nowadays, nanoscience and nanotechnology have tremendous applications in our daily life thanks to the excellent properties of nanomaterials that allow for the development of advanced materials and functional systems (Bhushan 2016; Omietimi et al. 2023). One of the primary goals of nanotechnology and nanoscience is to create nanomaterials that are appropriate for various applications. Nanomaterials have dimensions ranging from 1 to 100 nanometers, and they have the potential to be utilized in various areas, including biosensors. Nanomaterials are present in several forms, including metal nanoparticles, metal oxide nanoparticles, carbon-based nanoparticles, polymeric nanoparticles, lipid-based nanoparticles and quantum dots (QDs). QDs are a crucial substance in nanotechnology, with potential uses in medicine and Graphene quantum dots (G-QDs) are a form of quantum dot that takes advantage of the unique features of graphene. In 2008, Ponomarenko and Geim developed G-QDs, which opened up new possibilities among other nanostructures. G-QDs may constitute a small part of nanotechnology science, but it has become a fascinating topic in recent years. The diameter of graphene particles is often less than 100 nanometers, and they are described as being on the nanoscale (Gozali Balkanloo, Mohammad Sharifi, and Poursattar Marjani 2023). Several studies have demonstrated the feasibility of producing G-QDs from biological waste materials. This process, often referred to as "waste-to-treasure," is considered environmentally sustainable and is recognized for its eco-friendly benefits (Ahmet Aykaç, Souhaila Elalaoui 2024).

G-QDs are zero-dimensional, carbon-based fluorescent nanomaterials with distinct features such as biocompatibility, nontoxicity, and controllable light emission. These properties make G-QDs ideal for clinical diagnostics, as their size and composition may be adjusted to individual purposes. Their great solubility in water and low toxicity makes them excellent for bioimaging, biosensing, and cancer treatment. G-QDs display photoluminescence (PL), which is the emission of light caused by electron excitation during photon absorption. These quantum dots' emission wavelengths can be changed by varying their size, changing their surface characteristics, or adding dopants like nitrogen or boron into the carbon lattice. Optimizing G-QDs' light wavelengths for specific applications increases their usefulness in bio-imaging and biosensing systems. G-QDs are also used in nanosensors, drug delivery, photocatalysis, and photovoltaics because of their unique features, such as quantum confinement and edge effects. (Kuznetsov 2022; J. S. Lee et al. 2018; Kortel et al. 2020; Kost, Mauro, and Da Ros 2023; Samir et al. 2012; Tilwani et al. 2015).

Figure 1. Graphene Quantum Dots Structure (G-QDs)

For the purpose of producing nanostructures such as G-QDs, numerous types of studies have been carried out on natural organic waste materials. These materials include coconut husk, nutmeg seed, mint leaves, coffee beans, and tea leaves (Kharangarh et al. 2023). Coffee is one of the most popular non-alcoholic beverages, with a worldwide consumption rate of 2.25 billion cups per day. And it's famous for its aroma and caffeine content (Singh et al. 2022). Global coffee production generates over 10 million tons of waste annually, including fresh coffee cherry pulp, old grounds, and takeout cups. Some of it is recycled, but the vast majority of it is disposed of in landfills, rivers, and oceans. The circular economy concept aims to recycle waste into input resources, but estimates suggest the sector could generate over 23 million tons annually, posing environmental risks (Y. G. Lee et al. 2023; Tamilselvan et al. 2024). Tea is one of the most popular beverages, after water. Global tea consumption is expected to rise from 6.3 million tons in 2020 to 7.4 million tons by the end of 2025. As a result of the massive increase in tea consumption, waste tea leaves (WTL) production have increased significantly. As explained above, several studies have been conducted on the conversion of tea leaves and coffee beans waste into high value-added nanomaterials. At this point, in this study, we synthesized G-QDs with a simple, fast, practical and cheap method using coffee and tea waste as precursors of QDs. (Debnath, Haldar, and Purkait 2022; Y. G. Lee et al. 2023; Duarah et al. 2024).

Materials and Methods

Quantum dot synthesis can be broadly categorized into two primary approaches: a) top-down and b) bottom-up. In the top-down technique, big carbon compounds are broken down into nanosized particles through the use of physical forces. In contrast, the bottom-up approach initiates with precursor materials in the form of nanosize particles and employs microwave-assisted techniques to transform these precursor molecules into nanoparticles. Several methods are available for manufacturing G-QDs, with each method employing specific procedures for generating the required nanostructures. Laser ablation uses a laser to disintegrate graphite or other carbon sources, whereas hydrothermal and microwave reactions rely on elevated temperatures and pressures. The microwave-assisted method is a synthesis approach where precursor materials are dissolved in a solvent and heated to a hydrothermal temperature inside a reaction vessel while being subjected to microwave radiation (Prabhu et al. 2021; Li et al. 2017; Chen et al. 2018; Kadian, Sethi, and Manik 2021; Ahmet Aykaç, Souhaila Elaloui 2024).

Materials

Hydrazine hydrate 55% (H_4N_2) and Ethylene glycol 99.8% ($\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{OH}$) were purchased from Sigma Aldrich and used without any further purifications unless stated. WCB and WTL was obtained after brewing coffee beans and tea leaves in a domestic filter coffee and tea machines, and distilled water (dH_2O) were used as solvent for extrating the tea leaves and coffee bean waste.

Hettich Zentrifugen Universal 320 centrifuge, Thermomac TMC212 Centrifuge and Spectra/Por 3 Dialysis Tubing, 3.5 kD MWCO for purifications, BIOBASE lyophilizator for freeze drying, SAMSUNG MS23F300E home type-microwave for microwave-assisted synthesis, Elmasonic ultrasonic bath for cleaning the glassware have been used.

Methods

Preparation of G-QDs from tea leaves (G-QDs1, G-QDs2)

G-QDs were obtained from WTL using two different solvents. For G-QDs1, one gram of WTL powder was weighed and placed in a beaker, then 100 mL of ethanol was added. This extract was mixed in a thermomagnetic stirrer for 24 hours at room temperature and transferred to a 250 mL Erlenmar flask. After filtering the mixture using filter paper, it was heated in a microwave oven at 100 Watt for 13 minutes. For purification, use a centrifuge to remove large carbon particles by centrifuging the mixture at 5000 rpm for 20 minutes and then at 9000 rpm for 15 minutes. The obtained supernatant was filtered with a microporous membrane to remove the remaining residue. Last supernatant containing G-QDs was collected. While characterizing each solution, the stock solution was placed in the refrigerator and then lyophilized to obtain a powder of the synthesized G-QDs. The process involved one-step green synthesis of biomass-derived graphene quantum dots, which served as a highly selective optical sensing probe. This process is the same for G-QDs2 as shown in Figure 2, but the solvents were 10 mL of hydrozine hydrate and 90 mL of dH_2O .

Figure 2. Synthesis process of G-QDs from WTL with two different solvents

Preparation of G-QDs from coffee waste grounds (G-QDs3)

The biological green synthesis of G-QDs3 began with the combination of 1 gram of ground coffee waste powder, 10 ml of hydrazine hydrate, and 90 ml of dH_2O in a 250 ml beaker. After being mixed for 24 hours at room temperature using a thermomagnetic stirrer, the liquid was poured into a 250 ml Erlenmeyer flask. Subsequently, the mixture was filtered through filter paper and heated at 100 watts for 13 minutes. Large carbon particles were removed from the final solution by centrifuging it for 20 minutes at 5000 rpm and then for another 15 minutes at 9000 rpm. In order to remove any residue that may have been leftover, the supernatant was filtered through a microporous membrane after it had been collected. The supernatant, which contained the G-QDs, was collected. Each solution was characterized, while the stock solution was stored in a refrigerator and later lyophilized to produce a powder form of the synthesized G-QDs, as shown in figure 3.

Figure 3. Synthesis process of G-QDs from WCG with certain solvents

Characterization

The characterization of G-QDs involves various techniques, including spectroscopic, optical, and microscopic techniques. (i) Spectroscopic methods include Raman spectroscopy, PL, and X-ray photoelectron spectroscopies (XPS). These techniques are used to analyze the fluorescence properties, functional groups, and vibrational patterns of G-QDs. (ii) Optical methods investigate G-QDs' unique properties, such as low toxicity, good solubility, tunable photoluminescence (PL), biocompatibility, and photo-induced electron transfer. (iii) Microscopic techniques such as transmission electron microscopy (TEM), atomic force microscopy (AFM), and X-ray diffraction (XRD) are utilized for analyzing G-QDs surface morphologies and crystalline structure and to study the structure and crystalline nature, respectively (Gomez et al. 2021; Kundu and Pillai 2020).

Results and Discussion

Ultraviolet Visible Spectrometry

Ultraviolet Visible Spectrometry (UV-VIS spectrometry) is a cost-effective method for analyzing nanomaterials by comparing the ultraviolet light intensity reflected from a sample with a references. As demonstrated in figure 4, the special pick for G-QDs at 270 nm is the same as what was found in the study that was conducted by Filimon Hadish and colleagues (Hadish et al. 2022).

Figure 4. UV-VIS spectrometry characterization technique for three different G-QDs

Dynamic light scattering (DLS)

DLS is a sensitive, non-intrusive analytical tool used for characterizing macromolecules and colloids in solution, as well as measuring the size and distribution profile of nanoparticles. Figure 5 illustrates the intensity distribution, which is the most obvious outcome of a DLS experiment. This distribution is based on the scattering light intensity as a function of particle size. Larger particles scatter more light than smaller particles, resulting in a skewed intensity distribution toward larger particles, regardless of

quantity. Therefore, in figure 5. it observes three distinct scatter light results for each of the three G-QDs that scatter light from their particles, with G-QDs1 exhibiting the best result at approximately 88 nm (Farkas and Kramar 2021; Jia et al. 2023).

Figure 5. DLS analysis by intensity including three different graphene quantum dots a) G-QDS1, b) G-QDS2 and c) G-QDS3

Zeta potential

Generally, zeta potential takes place at either +30 or -30 mV to distinguish between stable and unstable suspensions. Particles with zeta potentials more positive than +30 mV or more negative than -30 mV are normally considered stable (Dukhin and Xu 2019). For the zeta potential characterization method, the zeta potential was used for G-QDs1, which had the best DLS and UV-Vis spectrometry results among the three different G-QDs obtained in this experiment. So, there is a pick of -36.9 mV in figure 6., which means that G-QDs1 stabilization is quite suitable and encourages us to pursue other characterization methods.

Results

	Mean (mV)	Area (%)	St Dev (mV)
Zeta Potential (mV): -36,9	Peak 1: -37,8	100,0	6,75
Zeta Deviation (mV): 18,7	Peak 2: 0,00	0,0	0,00
Conductivity (mS/cm): 0,00784	Peak 3: 0,00	0,0	0,00
Result quality Good			

Figure 6. Zeta potential analysis of G-QDs1

Conclusion and Future Perspective

Carbonizing residual resources (WTL and WCG) into G-QDs not only allows for recycling but also prevents them from being disposed of in landfills. In conclusion, WTL and WCG can be used as precursors for the environmentally friendly manufacture of highly fluorescent G-QDs by Microwave-assisted process, which is quick, cost-effective, and corresponds to the concepts of green chemistry.

Conclusively, we successfully synthesized G-QDs from biological green sources. Moreover, in a microwave-assisted synthesis technique, they were characterized by UV-Vis spectrometry, DLS (dynamic light scattering) and Zeta sizer. G-QDs exhibit outstanding optical properties and remain stable under a variety of storage and operational conditions. They are highly effective as fluorescent probes for the sensitive and specific detection of antioxidants, vitamins, dopamine, glucose, amino acids, and other substances.

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